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Late Holocene vegetation dynamics on an Atlantic–Mediterranean mountain in NW Iberia

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1 ABSTRACT

2 Detailed studies on the late Holocene vegetation dynamics of the mountains of
3 NW Iberia are rare. Furthermore, the impact of human activities and changes in fire
4 activity on the natural vegetation are not well-known over these areas. In order to
5 improve the knowledge on these topics, pollen and charcoal analyses were conducted on
6 two new sedimentary sequences from the Teleno Mountains. Between ca 4,500 and
7 3,200 cal yr BP, *Pinus* type *sylvestris* and *Betula* dominated the forests that covered the
8 uplands of the Teleno Mountains. At this point this pine-birch forest was replaced with
9 heathlands and grasslands, which persisted during all the Iron Age and the Roman
10 period until ca 1,500 cal yr BP. This abrupt deforestation process could be caused by
11 fire, grazing, and/or mining activities linked to the exploitation of the metal resources of
12 these mountains. Around 1,250 cal yr BP a *Betula* forest established in the uplands of
13 the Teleno Mountains, probably following a decrease in human activities. The gradual
14 rise in regional population density since ca 300-200 cal yr may be linked to the increase
15 in fire activity that triggered the replacement of birch forest with heathlands. Lastly, the
16 extent of the *Pinus pinaster*-dominated forests in the lowlands is an illustrative example
17 of how the economic activities of the local human population have controlled the
18 vegetation cover in this area, as it is very clear in the pollen record the recovery of
19 natural *Pinus pinaster* forests since ca AD 1900 associated to the start of resin
20 exploitation.

21 *Keywords:* *Pinus sylvestris*, fire ecology, pollen, macrofossils, Spain, *Betula*,
22 heathlands, charcoal, *Pinus pinaster*

23

24 **1. Introduction**

25 Many palaeoecological studies have been conducted in the NW Iberian
26 mountains during recent decades. The majority of the published palynological
27 sequences are from sites in the Eurosiberian region, although there are also few
28 palaeobotanical records from continental mountains located in the Mediterranean
29 region. This information has improved our knowledge of vegetation responses to
30 climate changes in this area during the late Quaternary (Allen et al., 1996; Muñoz
31 Sobrino et al., 2001, 2005, 2007). In the same way, recent palaeoecological records
32 have enhanced the role of NW Iberia as a glacial refuge area for temperate (Gómez-
33 Orellana et al., 2007) and Mediterranean trees (Ramil-Rego et al. 1998a) during
34 Pleistocene cold stages. Nevertheless, the present knowledge about late Quaternary
35 vegetation dynamics in NW Iberia is still incomplete. The vegetation development and
36 the timing of the first human-induced deforestation processes in the inner and
37 continental mountains of NW Iberia are especially interesting research questions, as
38 these areas are almost completely deforested at present. Although there are several
39 pollen sequences from this area, such as those from the Sanabria Lake area and the
40 surrounding mountains (Allen et al., 1996; Janssen, 1996; Muñoz Sobrino et al., 2004),
41 their chronologies are not accurate enough to track the late Holocene impact of human
42 activities on the landscape (with the exception of the La Roya sequence; Allen et al.,
43 1996).

44 Patterns of Holocene fire activity and their influence on vegetation dynamics
45 have been widely reported from many sites around the world (e.g., Clark, 1988;
46 Colombaroli et al., 2007; Gavin et al., 2007; Higuera et al., 2008), including several
47 sequences from central and SE Iberia (e.g., Carrión and van Geel, 1999; Carrión et al.,
48 2003; Franco-Múgica et al., 2005a). In contrast, detailed microscopic charcoal analysis

49 has not been frequently employed in the sequences from the Cantabrian Range and the
50 NW Iberian mountains, although there are some exceptions (e.g., García Antón et al.,
51 1997). The study of macrofossils can also help complete the interpretation of the
52 vegetation history, usually providing a higher taxonomic resolution than palynological
53 analysis and presenting a local origin (Birks and Birks, 2000). In the Iberian Peninsula,
54 studies assessing pollen and macrofossils are almost absent (García Antón et al., 1995;
55 Carrión-Marco et al., 2010).

56 In this context, we conducted a palaeoecological study in the Teleno Mountains,
57 a mountainous area of NW Iberia that is very close to the Iberian Central Plateau. Our
58 first aim was to improve the knowledge of the mid- to late-Holocene vegetation
59 dynamics of the innermost massifs of NW Iberia and discuss the similarities and
60 differences with other studied sites from N and W Iberia. We also aimed to reconstruct
61 the regional fire activity of this area by means of charcoal analysis to increase our
62 understanding of the long-term fire ecology of these Atlantic–Mediterranean mountains,
63 where lightning incidence is currently very high. Furthermore, this area has remained
64 almost continuously inhabited since the Bronze Age, and some of the occupation
65 periods are expected to have had an important impact on the natural vegetation, such as
66 the Roman period (when extensive mining activities took place; Matías, 2006).
67 Nevertheless, it is not clear how important the human impact was on the environment
68 during this period and to what extent had human activities altered the ‘natural’
69 vegetation when Romans arrived in the area. As a result of this, we aimed to evaluate
70 human impacts on the natural vegetation of this mountain range during the last
71 millennia and whether the impact depended on the considered altitudinal belt. To shed
72 new light on these three main questions, we conducted pollen, microscopic charcoal and

73 macrofossil analyses on two cores from different altitudinal belts of this mountainous
74 area.

75

76 **2. Study area**

77 The Teleno Mountains are located in the SW corner of the León province and
78 are one of the westernmost massifs of the Cantabrian Range (Fig. 1.a). This mountain
79 chain divides the Eria and Duerna basins (both tributaries of the Duero River) and runs
80 for approximately 40 km from NW to SE. Its highest peak is the Teleno Peak (2,183 m
81 a.s.l.). This area has two main geological units: 1) an Ordovician basement that is
82 mostly composed of quartzites and slates and 2) Quaternary deposits of variable grain
83 size that are located in the foothills of the massif (Sánchez Fernández, 2005a). As a
84 result, the soils developed over these rocks are acidic, shallow and coarse-grained. The
85 geomorphological setting is characterized by gentle slopes and quartzitic ridges at the
86 top of the mountains. Furthermore, glaciers must have been important in the northern
87 slopes of this mountain range, with moraines below 1,400 m a.s.l. in the area (Alonso
88 Otero, 1982). In addition, extensive scree slopes are one of the most characteristic
89 features of the Teleno Mountains landscape. This area is currently characterised by a
90 sub-Mediterranean climate. The mean annual temperature is approximately 10°C, and
91 the average annual rainfall is about 700 mm, with a summer drought that lasts for two to
92 three months (based on data from the meteorological station of Tabuyo del Monte,
93 1,000 m a.s.l.). The abundance of summer thunderstorms over the mountains is
94 remarkable.

95 At present, woodlands are rare in the area. The only remaining natural forests are
96 extensive woodlands dominated by *Pinus pinaster* Aiton on the eastern foothills of the

97 Teleno Mountains between 900 and 1,200 m a.s.l. (Fig. 1.b), certain small stands of
98 *Quercus pyrenaica* Willd. in valley bottoms reaching 1,500 m a.s.l. and riparian
99 corridors with several deciduous trees (*Betula pubescens* Ehrh., *Alnus glutinosa* (L.)
100 Gaertn., *Salix* spp., *Fraxinus excelsior* L., *F. angustifolia* Vahl, *Corylus avellana* L. and
101 *Populus tremula* L.). In contrast, the landscape is largely dominated by extensive
102 deforested areas that are covered by heathlands mainly composed of *Erica australis* L.,
103 *E. arborea* L., *E. umbellata* Loefl. ex L., *Calluna vulgaris* (L.) Hull, *Pterospartum*
104 *tridentatum* (L.) Willk. and *Halimium lasianthum* subsp. *alyssoides* (Lam.) Greuter
105 (Fig. 1.c). There are also some areas of broom-dominated shrublands (*Genista florida*
106 L., *Cytisus scoparius* (L.) Link), whereas the highest areas of the mountains are covered
107 by a prostrate shrubland dominated by *Juniperus communis* subsp. *alpina* (Suter)
108 Čelak., *Cytisus oromediterraneus* Rivas-Martínez *et al.* and *Genista sanabrensis* Valdés
109 Berm., Castrov. & Casaseca. This shrubland-dominated landscape is currently
110 associated with the high frequency of severe wildfires all over these mountains. These
111 fires are usually human-induced, but it is remarkable the high proportion of lightning-
112 induced fires in the Teleno Mountains compared with the adjacent mountain massifs
113 (Rey and Ruiz, 2005). At present, forest fire management in this area focuses on
114 preventing the occurrence of forest fires and minimizing their severity by reducing the
115 fuel loads and their continuity.

116

117 **3. Material and methods**

118 *3.1 Coring*

119 Two cores were obtained from the Teleno Mountains using a Russian corer. One
120 sampling location was at Arroyo de Vallefondo (referred to hereafter as Vallefondo)

121 (42°16'52"N, 6°12'10"W, 1,000 m a.s.l.), and the other sampling site was at Xan de
122 Llamas (42°18'15"N, 6°19'17"W, 1,500 m a.s.l.). The sampling locations are
123 approximately 10.5 km apart. Coring at the Vallefondo site stopped at 180 cm deep, and
124 only the uppermost 64 cm were rich in pollen. Preliminary results from this core were
125 published by Franco et al. (2005b). At the Xan de Llamas site, 135 cm of sediment was
126 retrieved. Core sections were stored in plastic drainpipes, wrapped in cling film and
127 kept at 4°C until chemical treatment took place.

128 Vallefondo is a small depression located at the bottom of a valley. Thus, the
129 pollen source area is predominantly local and reflects the pollen signal of the vegetation
130 surrounding the valley (Sugita, 1994; Bunting, 2002). However, a certain regional
131 signal is always recorded (Parshall and Calcote, 2001). At the present time, the site is
132 surrounded by a *Pinus pinaster* forest with a dense understory of heaths and *Halimium*
133 *lasianthum* subsp. *alyssoides*. In contrast, Xan de Llamas is a vast *Sphagnum* peat bog
134 with the presence of *Erica tetralix* L., *Genista anglica* L., *Molinia caerulea* (L.)
135 Moench., *Drosera rotundifolia* L., *Carex spp.* and *Potentilla erecta* (L.) Raeusch.
136 Currently, the highlands surrounding this peat bog are completely deforested and
137 covered with heathlands. Considering the area of the peat bog and the local
138 geomorphology, the pollen source area could comprise mainly the upper River Xandella
139 basin (approximately 12 km²), although certain regional pollen signal is also recorded
140 (Sugita, 1994; Parshall and Calcote, 2001; Bunting, 2002).

141

142 3.2 Radiocarbon dating and age-depth model

143 Four radiocarbon dates were obtained from the Xan de Llamas sequence, and
144 two dates were obtained from the Vallefondo sequence using standard AMS methods.

145 Throughout the text, ^{14}C ages have been converted to calendar years (following the
146 recommendations by Bartlein et al., 1995) using the program CALIB 6.0 (Stuiver and
147 Reimer, 1993) and the INTCAL09 calibration curve (Reimer et al., 2009). The median
148 age was used as an estimate of the calibrated ages from the radiocarbon dates (Telford
149 et al., 2004a) for constructing the age-depth models of the two sequences. Cubic spline
150 interpolation has been the selected age-depth model, taking into account the relatively
151 high number of dates related to the length of the sequences (Telford et al., 2004b).

152

153 *3.3 Pollen and microscopic charcoal analysis*

154 Thirty-three sediment samples 0.5 cm thick at 2- to 4-cm intervals were selected
155 for pollen analysis from the Xan de Llamas sequence (mean sediment accumulation
156 rate: $45.28 \text{ cal yr} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$), and sixteen sediment samples 0.5 cm thick were selected at 4-
157 cm intervals from the Vallefondo sequence (mean sediment accumulation rate: 13.87 cal
158 $\text{yr} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$). Each sample was treated following the standard procedures described by
159 Faegri and Iversen (1989). *Lycopodium* tablets were added at the beginning of the
160 treatment to estimate pollen concentration and the pollen accumulation rate (Stockmarr,
161 1971). Pollen sum, excluding spores and pollen of aquatic plants, was always
162 approximately 400 grains or higher. The reference collection at the *Laboratory of*
163 *Palynology of the Autonomous University of Madrid* was used to identify the pollen
164 types, along with the identification keys by Punt and Clarke (1984), Faegri and Iversen
165 (1989), Punt and Blackmore (1991) and Moore et al. (1991) and the photographic
166 atlases by Reille (1992, 1995). Local pollen assemblage zones (LPAZs) were delimited
167 using the optimal partitioning by information content method (Birks, 1986), and the
168 number of statistically significant zones was determined using the broken-stick model

169 (Bennett, 1996). Palynological richness, a proxy of plant diversity, was calculated using
170 rarefaction analysis (Birks and Line, 1992). The programs PSIMPOLL 4.27 and
171 PSCOMB 1.03 (Bennett, 2009) were used to plot the pollen diagrams and conduct the
172 statistical analyses.

173 Along with the pollen counts, microscopic charcoal particles longer than 10 μm
174 were counted on pollen slides at 200x magnification, following the recommendations of
175 Tinner and Hu (2003) and Finsinger and Tinner (2005). Charcoal particles were
176 identified following Clark's (1988) criteria. The microscopic charcoal concentration and
177 accumulation rate (CHAR) were estimated using the same approach as for pollen
178 analysis. These parameters are correlated with regional fire activity (MacDonald et al.,
179 1991; Tinner et al., 1998). To investigate possible relationships between regional fire
180 activity and changes in the vegetation cover, we calculated the existing correlations
181 between CHAR and pollen percentages of selected pollen types along the complete
182 sequences (Tinner et al., 1999; Colombaroli et al., 2007). The non-parametric
183 Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (r_s) was employed because the data did not
184 follow a normal distribution. We applied a t -test to determine whether the correlation
185 coefficients (r_s) were significantly different from 0 ($r_s \neq 0$, $\alpha = 5\%$, two-tailed, Tinner et
186 al., 2005). All statistical analyses were performed using the software STATISTICA 6.0
187 (Statsoft, Tulsa, Oklahoma).

188

189 3.4 Macroscopic charcoal and wood analysis

190 In the palynologically studied sections, we water-sieved the remaining sediment
191 to recover plant macrofossils. Thus, we obtained twenty-eight identifiable wood and
192 charcoal pieces from the Xan de Llamas core that we identified on the basis of their

193 wood anatomy. These macrofossils were most likely produced by plants that grew close
194 to the sedimentation area (Birks and Birks, 2000), although some cases of long-distance
195 transport of charcoal have been reported (Tinner et al., 2006). Wood and charcoal pieces
196 were manually fractured in three planes in relation to the wood structure: transverse,
197 radial and tangential. Next, they were examined using reflection microscopy (100–500x
198 magnification). The identification was made using common atlases and keys of wood
199 anatomy (Schweingrüber, 1990; Schoch et al., 2004) and comparing samples to the
200 reference collection at the *U.D. Botánica* of the *E.T.S.I. de Montes* (Technical
201 University of Madrid, Spain).

202

203 **4. Results**

204 *4.1 Lithostratigraphy and chronological framework*

205 Five lithostratigraphic units were identified in the Xan de Llamas sequence, and
206 three units were identified in the Vallefondo core. Table 1 shows the main features of
207 each unit: depth, colour, Troels-Smith (1955) notation and a brief description.

208 Radiocarbon dates obtained for both sequences are shown in Table 2, and the resulting
209 age-depth models have been incorporated in the pollen diagrams (Figs. 2-6).

210

211 *4.2 Pollen sequences*

212 Palynological sequences were quite diverse in pollen types. A total of 86 pollen
213 types were identified in the Xan de Llamas sequence, and 53 pollen types were
214 identified in the Vallefondo sequence. Pollen diagrams for Xan de Llamas are shown in
215 Figs. 2–4, and diagrams for Vallefondo are shown in Figs. 5–6. Moreover, Table 3

216 shows the data about rare pollen types in both sequences. The Xan de Llamas sequence
217 recorded the vegetation changes in the uplands of the Teleno Mountains over the last
218 4,000–4,500 cal yr BP, whereas the Vallefondo sequence showed the vegetation
219 development in the foothills of the same mountain range for the last 800–850 cal yr BP.
220 The Xan de Llamas sequence showed four statistically significant LPAZs (XL-1 to XL-
221 4), primarily responding to oscillations in the percentages of *Betula*, *Pinus*, Poaceae and
222 several Ericaceae taxa. LPAZs descriptions are summarised in Table 4. In contrast,
223 Vallefondo presented only three LPAZs (VF-1 to VF-3) that were associated with
224 changes in the proportions of *Betula*, *Pinus* and Ericaceae taxa. The main features of
225 these pollen zones are summarised in Table 5.

226

227 *4.3 Microscopic charcoal record*

228 Microscopic charcoal concentrations and CHAR estimates are shown in Figs. 4
229 and 6 for the Xan de Llamas and Vallefondo sequences, respectively. The chronological
230 evolution of these two parameters is summarised in Tables 4 and 5. The Xan de Llamas
231 sequence recorded a first small maximum around 3,300 cal yr BP in the CHAR curve
232 (ca 2,160 particles·cm⁻²·yr⁻¹). Another maxima in the CHAR curve were recorded ca
233 1850 cal yr BP, 850 cal yr BP, 300 cal yr BP and 100 cal yr BP, with values of ca 6,700
234 particles·cm⁻²·yr⁻¹, 5,700 particles·cm⁻²·yr⁻¹, 31,400 particles·cm⁻²·yr⁻¹ and 76,700
235 particles·cm⁻²·yr⁻¹, respectively. The main maxima recorded in the Vallefondo
236 sedimentary sequence were at ca 650 cal yr BP, 500 cal yr BP and 100 cal yr BP, when
237 CHAR values reached ca 38,000 particles·cm⁻²·yr⁻¹, 18,000 particles·cm⁻²·yr⁻¹ and
238 26,000 particles·cm⁻²·yr⁻¹, respectively.

239 Correlation analyses between CHARs and the percentages of several pollen
240 types are summarised in the correlograms in Fig. 7. The Xan de Llamas record showed
241 a positive and significant correlation between CHAR and Ericaceae, shrubs and several
242 taxa that are usually linked to human activities (e.g., *Castanea*, *Cerealia*, *Olea*,
243 *Artemisia* and *Rumex*). In contrast, *Salix*, trees, *Pinus* and Liliaceae were significantly
244 negatively correlated with fire activity. In addition, *Corylus* and *Betula* were negatively
245 correlated with CHAR, but this relationship was not statistically significant.
246 Palynological richness showed a negative and significant correlation with the abundance
247 of arboreal pollen ($r_s = -0.554$, $P < 0.05$), but is positively correlated with shrub ($r_s =$
248 0.4211 , $P < 0.05$) and herb pollen percentages ($r_s = 0.5625$, $P < 0.05$). There is also a
249 positive relationship between CHAR and palynological richness, but it is not
250 statistically significant ($r_s = 0.236$, $P > 0.05$). The only pollen type that showed a strong
251 positive and significant correlation with CHAR in the Vallefondo sequence was
252 Ericaceae. The scarcity of statistically significant correlations in this sequence may be
253 associated with the low number of samples analysed.

254

255 *4.4 Macroscopic charcoal and wood fragments*

256 The taxonomic composition of the wood and macroscopic charcoal fragments of
257 Xan de Llamas is reported in Table 6. Most charcoal fragments were well preserved and
258 allowed us to obtain the most precise taxonomic identification. Nevertheless, some
259 charcoal pieces were not optimally preserved and we could not reach a detailed
260 identification (e.g., *Pinus sp.*). There was good agreement between the results obtained
261 from pollen analysis and the wood and charcoal pieces.

262 A large group of samples corresponded to the *Pinus sylvestris* type. Currently,
263 this group comprises three Iberian species: *Pinus sylvestris* L., *P. nigra* Arnold and *P.*
264 *uncinata* Ramond ex DC. Considering the wood anatomy of these species, they can be
265 distinguished consistently only when mature wood is present (see Rubiales et al., 2008).
266 The small size of the studied samples, together with their bad state of preservation,
267 prevented us from identifying the samples to the species level. In addition, several wood
268 fragments corresponded to *Betula sp.*, but unfortunately it was not possible to
269 distinguish consistently between the two Iberian species of birch, *Betula pubescens*
270 Ehrh. and *B. pendula* Roth (Hellberg and Carcaillet, 2003).

271

272 5. Discussion

273 5.1 Vegetation history in the Xan de Llamas area

274 From the beginning of the sequence (ca 4,500 cal yr BP) and until ca 3,300 cal
275 yr BP, the pollen record suggests that the uplands of the Teleno Mountains must have
276 been mainly forested, according to the high arboreal pollen percentages (Zone XL-1).
277 *Pinus* and *Betula* dominated those forests, which had an Ericaceae-rich understorey.
278 The fragments of macroscopic charcoal found in this part of the sequence allowed us to
279 determine that the pines involved would have belonged to the *Pinus sylvestris* group.
280 The present (Costa et al., 1997) and late-Quaternary (Figueiral and Carcaillet, 2005;
281 Rubiales et al., 2008) distribution of the species included in this group (*Pinus sylvestris*,
282 *P. nigra* and *P. uncinata*) suggests that *Pinus sylvestris* was most likely the species
283 present in the Xan de Llamas area, but the absence of strobili and mature wood
284 prevented us from confirming this hypothesis. On the other hand, the pollen signal of
285 deciduous and evergreen *Quercus* was quite limited throughout the sequence, which

286 may be linked to the absence of forests dominated by these trees in the uplands but to
287 the presence of stands dominated most likely by *Quercus pyrenaica* (deciduous
288 *Quercus*) and *Q. ilex* subsp. *ballota* (Desf.) Samp. at lower altitudes (until
289 approximately 1,500 m a.s.l.). The persistence of pine forests dominating the landscape
290 until the late Holocene is not a common pattern in the Eurosiberian mountains of NW
291 Iberia (see in Fig. 8 the sites mentioned in the text), where pine woods were often
292 replaced by deciduous oak-dominated forests during the Lateglacial period or at the
293 onset of the Holocene (Maldonado, 1994; Muñoz Sobrino et al., 1997, 2001; Ramil-
294 Rego et al., 1998b; Moreno et al., in press). In contrast, on the inner and most
295 continental massifs of this area (in the transitional zone between the Eurosiberian and
296 Mediterranean regions), pine woods maintained a certain but decreasing importance
297 throughout the Holocene (Allen et al., 1996; Muñoz Sobrino et al., 2004). In this
298 context, La Baña peat bog constitutes an exception to this rule and the pine was the
299 dominant tree in the pollen sequence until the late Holocene (Janssen, 1996). Similarly,
300 the Xan de Llamas record allows us to suggest that the continental climate and the
301 resistance to invasion of the established pinewoods were important ecological factors
302 allowing the persistence until recent times of these forests on the drier continental
303 slopes and massifs of the Cantabrian Range and adjacent mountains (Rubiales et al.,
304 2010), such as the Teleno Mountains. In this regard, the current distribution of
305 Cantabrian relict stands of *P. sylvestris* (Costa et al., 1997) and the palaeoecological
306 record (García Antón et al., 1997; Rubiales et al., 2008) seem to agree with this
307 statement. This inertial development of pine forests throughout the Holocene is a
308 common pattern with other sub-Mediterranean and Mediterranean Iberian mountains,
309 such as the Iberian Range (Peñalba, 1994), the Betic Ranges (Carrión et al., 2001, 2004)
310 and the Central System (Franco-Múgica et al., 1998, 2001a). Moreover, the pattern of

311 *Pinus* forests dominance throughout the Holocene has been also reported from the
312 Northern Iberian Plateau, which is characterised by a highly continental climate
313 (Franco-Múgica et al., 2001b, 2005a; García-Antón et al., 2011).

314 This forested landscape was abruptly replaced by heathlands and meadows at ca
315 3,200–3,300 cal yr BP (Zone XL-2) following a weak rise in fire activity and/or
316 increased land use (e.g., grazing). The presence of a highly inorganic silty-clay layer in
317 the lithostratigraphy of the Xan de Llamas sequence could be linked to this increase in
318 land use (burning, grazing). From that point in the record onwards, pollen spectra were
319 clearly dominated by several pollen types of Ericaceae, *Halimium* (most likely
320 representing *Halimium lasianthum* subsp. *alyssoides*), Poaceae, Apiaceae and Rosaceae.
321 Thus, heathlands and meadows would have been the main vegetation communities
322 covering the Xan de Llamas area. Their rapid establishment could have been favoured
323 by the soil erosion and impoverishment subsequent to the increased land use.
324 Furthermore, fire activity increased over this period and was accompanied by increases
325 in taxa that are adapted to perturbations and shallow and poor soils, such as *Erica*
326 *australis*, *Calluna vulgaris* and *Halimium lasianthum* subsp. *alyssoides*. This vegetation
327 persisted over this area until ca 1,300 cal yr BP and was probably linked to intense
328 mining and grazing activities. Another remarkable feature of this period is the marked
329 decline in the pollen percentages of *Pinus* and *Betula*.

330 The sudden demise of *Pinus sylvestris* forests in the Teleno Mountains area
331 during the late-Holocene is a highly remarkable process, especially taking into account
332 that these pine woods has become extinct during this period in most of the southern
333 slopes of the Cantabrian Range (Rubiales et al., 2008). Thus, well-established
334 pinewoods would have persisted throughout the Holocene in a climatic framework that
335 favoured broadleaved trees (Rubiales et al., 2008) but also suitable for *P. sylvestris*

336 (Benito Garzón et al., 2006), as a clear manifestation of biological inertia (Von Holle et
337 al., 2003). The presence of extensive areas covered with histosols in the highlands of the
338 Teleno Mountains could have facilitated the long-term persistence of this kind of forest
339 on these mountains, as has been suggested by Rubiales et al. (2008) for other
340 Cantabrian areas. Previously, several causes have been proposed as triggers for the
341 decline of pine forests in the Cantabrian area, such as human-induced changes in the
342 natural fire regimes, logging, grazing activities or even agriculture (García Antón et al.,
343 1997; Muñoz Sobrino et al., 2004; Rubiales et al., 2008). In this case, the microscopic
344 charcoal record suggests that wildfires could have played a role in triggering this sudden
345 decline, probably associated with grazing or other human activities. The almost non-
346 existent post-fire regeneration of the Iberian pine species included in the *Pinus sylvestris*
347 group following crown fires (Retana et al., 2002; Rodrigo et al., 2004), could have been
348 one of the causes of the non-recovery of the pinewoods in the uplands of the Teleno
349 Mountains.

350 Following this deforestation stage, an important forest recovery was recorded in
351 the Xan de Llamas sequence (Zone XL-3) at ca 1,300 cal yr BP. A decrease in human
352 activities was probably followed by the colonisation of open areas by *Betula*, a pioneer
353 tree that is well adapted to recruit its seedlings in heathlands and grasslands (Atkinson,
354 1992). The finding of several fragments of wood during this period (Table 6) provides
355 evidence of the local presence of these trees growing in the Xan de Llamas area. Birch-
356 dominated forests could have represented the timberline on acidic soils, a common
357 situation today in many of the westernmost areas of the Cantabrian Range and in the
358 Galician mountains (Costa et al., 1997). In addition to that, several late-Quaternary
359 palynological records of NW Iberia have suggested this role for birch woods (Allen et
360 al., 1996; Muñoz Sobrino et al., 1997). However, the sub-Mediterranean climate of

361 these inner massifs of NW Iberia could have restricted the predominance of these
362 forests to histosols, north-facing slopes or riparian habitats (van der Knaap and van
363 Leeuwen, 1994; Costa et al., 1997; Franco-Múgica et al., 2001a). The *Pinus* pollen
364 signal disappeared and evergreen and deciduous *Quercus* representation was reduced
365 during this period, perhaps because of an overrepresentation of *Betula* that may have
366 masked the regional pollen signal. Furthermore, several trees that seem to be cultivated
367 in this area began to be recorded in the pollen spectra along this interval, such as
368 *Castanea* (ca 750 cal yr BP = AD 1200) and *Juglans* (ca 450 cal yr BP = AD 1500), and
369 a continuous curve of *Olea* that starts during this zone (XL-3). *Cerealia*-type pollen
370 grains have been recognised since ca 750 cal yr BP (AD 1200). All these palynological
371 anthropogenic indicators could correlate with an intensification of farming in the
372 lowlands close to the Teleno Mountains.

373 Around 250 cal yr BP, an abrupt increase in the CHAR curve was noticed,
374 which may be linked to an important rise in fire activity. Consequently, *Betula* began its
375 decline, and the heathlands became the dominant vegetation community again. The
376 post-fire replacement of forests by heathlands must have been a common process in
377 these mountains of NW Iberia during the late-Holocene (Maldonado, 1994; Janssen,
378 1996; Carrión-Marco et al., 2010), and the heathlands are currently the main hallmark of
379 these territories (Costa et al., 1997). The palynological indicators of grazing increased at
380 this time (*Rumex*, Rosaceae and *Plantago lanceolata*) because perhaps humans set fire
381 to the birch woods to establish pasturelands. Furthermore, chestnut and olive orchards
382 must have increased in number and importance in the lowlands during recent centuries
383 because their pollen curves became continuous and their proportions, higher. This
384 process could have occurred in the El Bierzo area, a small depression close to the
385 Teleno Mountains with a marked Mediterranean climate, where are currently located the

386 nearest olive and chestnut groves. The *Pinus* pollen curve reappeared at this stage,
387 which was perhaps partly due to the recent expansion of *P. pinaster* in the lowlands (see
388 the vegetation history derived from the Vallefondo sequence below).

389

390 5.2 The last millennium in the lowlands of the Teleno Mountains

391 At the bottom of the Vallefondo sequence (ca 850 cal yr BP) the pollen record
392 suggests that the vegetation was clearly dominated by heathlands (Ericaceae and
393 *Halimium*) around the cored site. This community persisted over the LPAZs VF-1 and
394 VF-2 (i.e., until ca 350 cal yr BP). *Betula* was present in the landscape, most likely
395 composing riparian forests accompanied by *Alnus*, but became progressively less
396 important in the local landscapes while the shrublands increased their dominance.
397 Perhaps these birch-dominated stands experienced a decline linked to logging or
398 overgrazing, as there was no correspondence between fire activity and their demise in
399 this area. Moreover, evergreen and deciduous *Quercus* were scarcely represented
400 throughout the sequence and *Pinus* maintained a regular but reduced representation in
401 the pollen spectra. The pine species producing the pollen recorded in the sequence was
402 probably *P. pinaster*, taking into account its ecological requirements, and the finding of
403 *Pinus pinaster* charcoal fragments in a Roman mining site close to the studied bog
404 (Domergue and Herail, 1978). The important forest recovery (mainly of birch woods)
405 that took place on the highlands of the Teleno Mountains and the dominance of
406 deforested landscapes in the foothills suggest that the human activities concentrated in
407 the lowlands during this period (Fig. 9).

408 During this heathland-dominated stage, a gradual rise in the representation of
409 *Pinus* (from ca 500 cal yr BP onwards) began and has been reinforced since ca 350 cal

410 yr BP until the present time. Currently, pine forests with a dense understory of
411 Ericaceae and *Halimium* cover a wide area around the study site. One striking difference
412 with the highlands' vegetation history is the increase in the forest cover during recent
413 centuries and the absence of a clear increasing trend in the proportion of taxa associated
414 with grazing activities. This recent expansion of pine woods could have originated from
415 the isolated and reduced populations registered during LPAZs VF-1 and VF-2.

416

417 *5.3 Long-term fire ecology in the Teleno Mountains*

418 The Xan de Llamas palaeoecological record showed a strong negative
419 correlation between the *Pinus* representation in the landscape and fire incidence (Fig. 7).
420 The identified macroscopic charcoal fragments allow us to specify that those pines must
421 have mainly belonged to the *P. sylvestris* group. Our data are in accordance with several
422 studies on the fire ecology of these pine species (i.e., *P. sylvestris*, *P. nigra* and *P.*
423 *uncinata*) which have shown that they cannot regenerate after crown fires because they
424 lack serotinous cones (Tapias et al., 2004) and their pine kernels are very sensitive to
425 high temperatures (Escudero et al., 1999). However, this group of pines (especially *P.*
426 *syvestris*) presents a thick bark that is usually considered an adaptation to surface fires
427 (Tapias et al., 2004). Thus, the reported demise of *Pinus sylvestris*-dominated stands in
428 the uplands of the Teleno Mountains ca 3,300 cal yr BP, following a small maximum in
429 the CHAR curve, could have been caused by burning and grazing. The process of
430 replacing *P. sylvestris* and *P. nigra* forests by communities dominated by xerophytic
431 shrubs and fire-resilient pines and resprouters like *Quercus* has been reported in several
432 areas of NE Iberia at the decadal scale (Retana et al., 2002; Rodrigo et al., 2004).
433 Moreover, several palaeoecological studies from other sites in the Mediterranean basin

434 show a similar pattern over a longer temporal scale (Carrión and van Geel 1999; Gil-
435 Romera et al., 2010). In the Teleno Mountains, fire-adapted communities such as
436 grasslands and heathlands dominated by *Erica arborea*, *E. australis*, *Calluna vulgaris*
437 and *Halimium lasianthum* subsp. *alyssoides*, usually replaced forests after disturbance.
438 All these species are highly correlated with fire activity in our palaeoecological record
439 from Xan de Llamas (Fig.8).

440 Deforestation is one of the most important consequences of fires in this area
441 during the Holocene, as in other Mediterranean (Carrión et al., 2001; Colombaroli et al.,
442 2007) and Alpine areas (Tinner et al., 1999). In this context, the Xan de Llamas
443 sequence shows significant increases in palynological richness following forest
444 clearance processes, probably due to the establishment of several heliophilous species of
445 shrubs and herbs. Furthermore, fire activity seems to promote species diversity,
446 although this relationship is not very strong in this sequence. Thus, there is a positive
447 correlation between deforestation processes and the number of pollen types (Odgaard,
448 1999), but in this case it is not so clear the role of fire as the main factor favouring the
449 establishment of open environments and the increase in inferred plant diversity
450 (Colombaroli et al., 2009). In fact, in the mountains of NW Iberia, it does not seem to
451 exist a positive correlation between fire incidence and the importance of grasslands
452 (Fig. 7). The great fitness that heathlands have in these territories might have hindered
453 the dominance of grasslands in the landscape, and therefore the dominance of
454 heathlands is perhaps the most notable difference with the usual vegetation response
455 documented in other Mediterranean (Colombaroli et al., 2007; Tinner et al., 2009) or
456 Alpine sites (Tinner et al., 1999, 2005), where grasslands show a positive response to
457 fire incidence. Finally, the strong positive correlation between fire incidence and the
458 abundance of anthropogenic indicators, such as lowland crops (*Olea*, *Cerealia* and

459 *Castanea*) or plants associated with grazing (e.g., *Artemisia*, *Potentilla* and *Rumex*)
460 (Fig. 7), points to an important role of human activities in maintaining the fire regime
461 during the last millennia.

462

463 *5.4 Human impact on natural vegetation*

464 The beginning of the Xan de Llamas sequence (ca 4,500–3,200 cal yr BP) did
465 not record any important disturbance on the natural vegetation. The nearly absence of
466 anthropogenic indicators suggests that human activities were not a main determinant of
467 the fire regime during this period, although it is difficult to disentangle natural and
468 human causes of fire in the Mediterranean area (Vannire et al., 2010). Moreover, the
469 current high incidence of thunderstorms over this area and the abundance of lightning-
470 caused fires at present (Rey and Ruiz, 2005) lead us to suggest that lightning could be
471 an important cause of fire ignition during this period. Around 3,200 cal yr BP, there was
472 a drastic reduction in the pine forests in the highlands of the Teleno Mountains. What
473 could have caused this demise? On the one hand, the microscopic charcoal record shows
474 a small maximum that could be related with an increase in fire activity. On the other
475 hand, we must consider the impact of human activities such as grazing and/or mining.
476 Despite the scarce archaeological record of this area during the Chalcolithic and the
477 Bronze Age periods (ca 4,500–2,900 cal yr BP), there are several archaeological
478 findings from areas very close to Xan de Llamas (Fernndez Manzano, 1986). Thus,
479 humans could have set fire to the forests to favour the establishment of extensive
480 pastures for their livestock. Then, the subsequent heavy grazing pressure would have
481 hindered the recovery of the forest, as livestock farming must have been one of the
482 economic basis for these societies (Fernndez Manzano, 1986; Valbuena-Carabana et

483 al., 2010). Fire could also have been caused by lightning, but the absence of a
484 subsequent forest recovery for centuries seems to indicate that the human-induced fire
485 hypothesis is more likely than the lightning-induced fire hypothesis. The Bronze and Iron
486 Ages (3,500-1,700 cal yr BP) were also the periods when the onset of human
487 disturbance is recorded in several mountains of NW Iberia (Maldonado, 1994; Peñalba,
488 1994; van der Knaap and van Leeuwen, 1995; Janssen, 1996; Allen et al., 1996; Carrión
489 et al., 2010).

490 In the Teleno Mountains, the Iron Age is characterised by an increase in human
491 settlements and the beginning of mining activities at a local scale (Fernández Manzano,
492 1986; Sánchez Fernández, 2005a), thus maintaining a deforested landscape. In several
493 mountainous areas of SE Iberia, the development of societies with important mining
494 activities during the Chalcolithic and the Bronze Ages was linked to severe
495 deforestation processes (Carrión et al., 2003, 2007). Our palynological record shows
496 that deforested landscapes were widespread before Romans' arrival to NW Iberia, and
497 this situation must have been common over extensive areas of Europe (Kaplan et al.,
498 2009). However, a noticeable increase in the CHAR curve may reflect a further rise in
499 human activities in the Teleno Mountains during the Roman occupation. This was not
500 only due to the high density of mining structures during this period (Matías, 2006) and
501 the high amounts of charcoal needed to melt the raw ore into usable gold or silver
502 (Edmonson, 1989) but also to the high population densities associated with the mining
503 activities and their needs to survive (Sánchez Fernández, 2005a).

504 The Middle Ages (ca 1,500 to 400 cal yr BP) were a period of forest recovery in
505 the highlands of the Teleno Mountains, probably due to the drop in mining activities
506 and the subsequent depopulation process. The deforested landscape that shows the
507 Vallefondo sequence along this interval may indicate a concentration of the human

508 activities in the foothills of the Teleno Mountains. This medieval forest recovery must
509 have been an extended trend all over Castile, as indicated by a study of the historical
510 sources (Valbuena-Carabaña et al., 2010). From ca 250 cal yr BP onwards, new
511 deforestation processes occurred in the Xan de Llamas area, leading to a heathland-
512 dominated landscape again. This change could be linked to the increasing human
513 population and the existence of an intense livestock grazing (mainly goats in the
514 uplands; Sánchez Fernández, 2005a). In addition, fire activity increased during this
515 period, and perhaps most of the fires were associated with the establishment and
516 improvement of pasturelands, as occurs today in many mountain ranges of northern
517 Iberia. The last remarkable process of vegetation dynamics associated with human
518 activities is the recovery of the *Pinus pinaster* forests in the surroundings of the
519 Vallefondo site during the last century linked to the onset and development of resin
520 exploitation, which became a keystone socio-economic activity around AD 1898 (52 cal
521 yr BP) (Sánchez Fernández, 2005b). Pine forests expanded mainly from the rocky
522 outcrops where they survived the intense human disturbances (Fig. 1.b), as described by
523 Madoz in 1850 (Sánchez Fernández, 2005a). From this point onwards, humans would
524 have favoured the re-establishment of these pine forests in the lowlands of the Teleno
525 Mountains, until their current extent of approximately 13,000 ha.

526

527 **6. Conclusions**

528 We confirm the long-term persistence of pine forests (mostly *P. sylvestris*) in the
529 inner and most continental massifs of NW Iberia until the late-Holocene. This pattern of
530 Holocene vegetation development is very different from those usually recorded in other
531 Atlantic areas of Europe. Moreover, the extinction or extreme reduction of this forest

532 type is most likely associated with changes in land use that promoted burning and
533 grazing over these highlands.

534 Pollen and microscopic charcoal analyses, together with correlation analyses,
535 have confirmed the importance and stability of heathlands in these Atlantic areas where
536 both fire recurrence and fire intensity are high. It seems to be difficult for trees to
537 colonise these areas, except when disturbance regimes decrease markedly, allowing a
538 pioneer tree, such as birch, to establish itself in the dense shrublands. However, the
539 response of *Betula* to fire occurrence is negative, which contrasts the behaviour of this
540 genus in other areas. The sub-Mediterranean climate of these areas, with certain summer
541 drought, may be the underlying cause.

542 Most of the detected vegetation changes can be associated with oscillations in
543 human population density and socio-economic processes. In contrast with the common
544 assumption that Romans were the civilisation that caused the first great deforestation
545 process over this mountainous area, it seems that the Romans found a deforested
546 landscape when they arrived in the Teleno area. The final recovery of *Pinus pinaster* in
547 the lowlands is a good example of how changing economic activities can lead to
548 vegetation changes. The increase in the value of the resin obtained from this pine
549 species reduced the pressure of livestock grazing on these foothills and favoured the
550 recovery of these pine stands, which had previously become nearly extinct due to high
551 human pressure.

552 At present, rural depopulation and subsequent land abandonment are widespread
553 over extensive areas of NW Iberia. These ongoing land use changes are promoting even
554 more the dominance of heathlands over the landscape. These vegetation types are
555 characterised by their high flammability, and therefore it is likely that fire incidence is

556 going to increase in the near future. On the other hand, European forest policies are
557 currently promoting the recovery of the ‘natural’ vegetation cover, which is often
558 unknown in these areas with a long history of human occupation. Our palaeoecological
559 study in the Teleno Mountains provides insights on the vegetation composition before
560 the onset of an intense human impact and the secondary succession after severe
561 disturbances. Thus, it can help to guide current efforts to restore vegetation in these
562 mountainous areas with ‘pristine’ and less flammable vegetation communities like Scots
563 pine and birch forests.

564

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845

846 **Tables**

847 **Table 1.** Lithostratigraphy of the Xan de Llamas (XL) and the Vallefondo (VF)
 848 cores. The palynologically sterile section of the Vallefondo sequence has not been
 849 considered.

Core	Depth (cm)	Colour	Troels-Smith (1955) notation	Sediment description
XL	20–71	Black	Tb2T11Th1	<i>Sphagnum</i> peat with Ericaceae and Cyperaceae roots
XL	71–84	Dark brown	Tb2T11D11	<i>Sphagnum</i> peat with some small pieces of wood and ligneous roots interbedded
XL	84–110	Dark grey	Tb2As2	<i>Sphagnum</i> peat with clay
XL	110–115	Pale yellow	As2Ag2	Silty clay
XL	115–135	Yellowish grey	As2Ag1D11	Silty clay with wood charcoal pieces
VF	0-7	Brown	Th2Ag2	Sedge peat with clay
VF	7-42	Greyish brown	Ag2As1Ld1	Organic clayey silt
VF	42-62	Yellowish brown	Ag3As1	Clayey silt

850

851 **Table 2.** Radiocarbon datings obtained from the Xan de Llamas (XL) and
 852 Vallefondo (VF) sequences.

Core	Laboratory number	Material	Depth (cm)	Conventional ¹⁴ C age (yr BP)	Calibrated age (cal yr BP) (2σ, p=0.954)*	Median calibrated age (cal yr BC/AD)*
XL	β-267421	Peat	35–37	100.2 ± 0.5 pMC	0	AD 1950
XL	β-267422	<i>Betula</i> wood	72	820 ± 40	892–673	AD 1219
XL	β-270772	Organic sediment	106–107	2450 ± 40	2706–2359	570 BC
XL	β-146012	Organic sediment	118–120	3270 ± 40	3607–3396	1551 BC
VF	β-146011	Organic sediment	30–33	490 ± 40	626–485	AD 1426
VF	β-267420	Organic sediment	56–57	840 ± 40	901–679	AD 1199

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854 * Calibrated ages were obtained using CALIB 6.0 software (Stuiver & Reimer,
 855 1993) with the calibration dataset INTCAL09 (Reimer et al., 2009).

856

857 **Table 3.** Rare pollen types in the Xan de Llamas (XL) and the Vallefondo (VF)
 858 sequences. Only presence data are shown, as pollen percentages are always lower than
 859 1%.

Pollen type	Depth (cm)	Pollen type	Depth (cm)	Pollen type	Depth (cm)
<i>Acer</i>	XL 41, 110; VF 29	<i>Buxus</i>	XL 41	<i>Cirsium</i> type	VF 1
<i>Ulmus</i>	XL 88, 100, 110	<i>Scabiosa</i>	XL 92; VF 5, 25, 37, 57	<i>Armeria</i> type	VF 53
<i>Tilia</i>	XL 68, 114	<i>Asphodelus</i>	XL 34, 41, 72, 88; VF 49	<i>Ranunculus</i> type	VF 5, 45
<i>Fagus</i>	VF 29	Liliaceae	VF 13, 53, 57	<i>Thalictrum</i>	XL 61, 110
<i>Salix</i>	VF 17, 41, 45, 49	Gentianaceae	XL 96, 108, 110, 116	<i>Myriophyllum verticillatum</i>	XL 56; VF 5, 9
<i>Juglans</i>	VF 5	Convolvulaceae	VF 25	<i>Potamogeton</i>	XL 31
<i>Sambucus</i>	VF 9	Lamiaceae	VF 5	<i>Callitriche</i>	XL 27, 31, 41, 72
<i>Frangula</i>	XL 34, 128	Rubiaceae	VF 5, 29, 33	<i>Typha</i>	XL 100, 134
<i>Pistacia</i>	XL 38	<i>Sanguisorba minor</i> type	VF 9, 33	<i>Alisma</i> type	XL 88, 92, 112
<i>Hedera</i>	XL 72, 92; VF 17	<i>Polycarpon</i> type	XL 108	<i>Polygonum persicaria</i> type	XL 112
<i>Lonicera</i>	XL 80	<i>Illecebrum verticillatum</i> type	XL 96	<i>Juncus</i>	XL 88, 92
<i>Ligustrum</i>	XL 24, 114	<i>Hypericum perforatum</i> type	XL 45	<i>Equisetum</i>	VF 9
Thymelaeaceae	XL 118	<i>Aster</i> type	VF 17, 25, 37, 41		
<i>Vitis</i>	XL 61	<i>Centaurea nigra</i> type	VF 45		

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Table 4. Local pollen assemblage zones (LPAZ) corresponding to the Xan de

863 Llamas (XL) sequence.

LPAZ	Depth (cm)	Estimated age (cal yr BP)	Description
XL-4	24–54	250–(AD 1998)	Progressive decline of tree pollen, reaching a relative abundance below 10% at the top of the sequence. Ericaceae was clearly the dominant pollen type (44–66%) throughout this period. It is noticed an increase in the representation of pollen indicating grazing (<i>Plantago lanceolata</i> , <i>Rumex</i> and Rosaceae). Continuous curves of <i>Olea</i> , <i>Castanea</i> and <i>Cerealia</i> . High charcoal accumulation rate values, with an important maximum at ca 100 cal yr BP.
XL-3	54–86	1300–250	Significant increase in arboreal pollen, mainly <i>Betula</i> (50–62%). <i>Pinus</i> continued its decrease, disappearing from the pollen spectra. Sporadic record of <i>Fagus</i> . Ericaceae and Poaceae presented low values throughout this zone. The first records of <i>Castanea</i> (ca 750 cal yr BP), <i>Cerealia</i> (ca 750 cal yr BP) and <i>Juglans</i> (ca 450 cal yr BP) pollen appeared. Moderate to very low charcoal accumulation rate values existed, except at the top of the zone (ca 350–250 cal yr BP) where there was a marked increase.
XL-2	86–111	2850–1300	Important rise in the relative abundance of pollen from shrubs and herbs (79–86%), mainly Poaceae (17–40%), Apiaceae (3–9%) and Ericaceae (20–42%). There were higher values of <i>Halimium</i> -type and a marked drop in <i>Betula</i> and <i>Pinus</i> pollen percentages. One <i>Fagus</i> pollen grain was recorded at ca 1600 cal yr BP. There was an increase in the charcoal accumulation rate from ca 2000 cal yr BP onwards.
XL-1	111–134	4650–2850	High arboreal pollen values (60–79%), dominated by <i>Pinus</i> (20–53%) and <i>Betula</i> (12–36%). Ericaceae were well represented. Both evergreen and deciduous <i>Quercus</i> were present in relatively low pollen percentages along the whole sequence. There were low charcoal accumulation rate values, but a small maximum was recognised at ca 3250 cal yr BP.

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Table 5. Local pollen assemblage zones (LPAZ) of the Arroyo de Vallefondo

867 (VF) sequence.

LPAZ	Depth (cm)	Estimated age (cal yr BP)	Description
VF-3	0–19	300–(AD 1998)	Tree pollen rose strongly (from 19% to 51%), associated with a marked increase in <i>Pinus</i> relative abundance. Subsequently, shrub pollen showed a sharp decline until it reached 42%. There were moderate levels of charcoal accumulation rates, with a maximum at ca 100 cal yr BP.
VF-2	19–39	600–300	Shrub pollen continued its dominance, with even higher percentages (72–80%). Ericaceae and <i>Halimium</i> -type were the main taxa recorded within this group. <i>Betula</i> strongly declined in this period, whereas <i>Pinus</i> slightly increased at the top of this zone (from 1.6% to 11%). There were medium levels of charcoal accumulation rate.
VF-1	39–62	800–600	There was a predominance of shrub pollen (46–73%), mainly Ericaceae and <i>Halimium</i> -type. <i>Betula</i> (14–37%) was the main arboreal pollen. <i>Pinus</i> and deciduous <i>Quercus</i> pollen was recorded scarce but continuously. <i>Cerealia</i> -type was sparsely recognised. Charcoal accumulation rate values were moderate, but there was a maximum ca 650 cal yr BP.

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870

Table 6. Absolute frequencies of macrofossils identified from the Xan de

871 Llamas sequence.

Type/Depth (cm)	35-37	65	66	68	72	116	122	128
<i>Erica sp.</i> charcoal	5							
<i>Betula</i> wood		1	4	1	1			
<i>Pinus sp.</i> charcoal							1	2
<i>Pinus</i> type <i>sylvestris</i> charcoal						6	1	6

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876

877 **Fig. 1.** a) Map showing the study area of the Teleno Mountains in NW Iberia. White
 878 stars represent the exact location of the two sampling sites: Xan de Llamas and
 879 Vallefondo. b) Landscape close to the Vallefondo area. *Pinus pinaster* forest on
 880 quartzite outcrops, where this species survived high human impact periods with
 881 increased fire activity and/or logging. c) Landscape of the Teleno Mountains highlands
 882 (Xan de Llamas area), which is covered mainly by extensive heathlands. The Teleno
 883 Peak is in the background (2,183 m a.s.l.).

884

885

886 **Fig. 2.** Pollen percentage diagram of the Xan de Llamas site: trees and shrubs (selected
 887 taxa). Black dots represent pollen frequencies less than 0.5%. Empty curves are
 888 exaggerated ten-fold. Lithology: 1 Peat with abundant roots, 2 Peat with wood
 889 fragments, 3 Clayey peat, 4 Silty clay, 5 Silty clay with charcoal pieces.

890

Xan de Llamas, Leon, Spain, 1500 m a.s.l.

897

898 **Fig. 4.** Synthetic pollen and charcoal diagram of the Xan de Llamas site. Pollen
 899 frequencies are represented as percentages, with black dots representing percentages
 900 below 0.5%. PAR = pollen accumulation rate, CHAR = charcoal accumulation rate
 901 (particles > 10 μ m long). Empty curves are exaggerated ten-fold. Lithology: 1 Peat with
 902 abundant roots, 2 Peat with wood fragments, 3 Clayey peat, 4 Silty clay, 5 Silty clay
 903 with charcoal pieces.

908

909 **Fig. 6.** Synthetic pollen and charcoal diagram of the Arroyo de Vallefondo site. Pollen
 910 frequencies are represented as percentages, with black dots representing percentages
 911 below 0.5%. PAR = pollen accumulation rate, CHAR = charcoal accumulation rate
 912 (particles > 10 μ m long). Empty curves are exaggerated ten-fold. Lithology: 1 Clayey
 913 peat, 2 Organic clayey silt, 3 Clayey silt.

914

915 **Fig. 7.** Correlograms showing Spearman's rank correlation coefficients between CHAR
 916 (particles · cm⁻² · yr⁻¹) and selected pollen types for: A) Xan de Llamas sequence, and
 917 B) Vallefondo sequence. Correlation coefficients outside the dotted lines are significant
 918 at P = 0.05.

919

920 **Fig. 8.** Situation map showing the location of the main palaeoecological sites on the
 921 NW Iberian ranges discussed in the text: (1) Vallefondo (Franco *et al.*, 2005b; this
 922 study), (2) Xan de Llamas (this study), (3) La Baña (Janssen, 1996), (4) Laguna de la
 923 Roya (Allen *et al.*, 1996), (5) Laguna de las Sanguijuelas (Muñoz Sobrino *et al.*, 2004),
 924 (6) Lagoa de As Lamas (Maldonado, 1994), (7) Lagoa de Lucenza (Muñoz Sobrino *et*
 925 *al.*, 2001), (8) Pozo do Carballal (Muñoz Sobrino *et al.*, 1997), (9) Vega de Viejos
 926 (Rubiales *et al.*, 2008), (10) Lago de Ajo (Allen *et al.*, 1996), (11) Pinar de Lillo (García
 927 Antón *et al.*, 1997), (12) Lago Enol (Moreno *et al.*, in press), (13) Quintanar de la Sierra
 928 (Peñalba, 1994), (14) Pelagallinas (Franco *et al.*, 2001), (15) Rascafría (Franco *et al.*,
 929 1998), (16) Charco da Candieira (van der Knaap & van Leeuwen, 1995) and (17) Lagoa
 930 do Marinho (Ramil-Rego *et al.*, 1998b).

931

932 **Fig. 9.** Comparison of the palaeoecological records from Xan de Llamas and Arroyo de
 933 Vallefondo, in the Teleno Mountains. Pollen percentage curves of several selected
 934 pollen types are represented together with the CHAR curves. Black dots symbolise
 935 pollen frequencies less than 0.5%. Empty curves are exaggerated ten-fold.